

Artificial Intelligence-Unstoppable in its Rise: Perceptual Study on Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Employment Opportunities

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:.
Kumari, K. Shobitha,
et al. "Artificial
Intelligence-Unstoppable
in Its Rise: Perceptual
Study on Impact of
Artificial Intelligence
on Employment
Opportunities." *Shanlax
International Journal
of Arts, Science and
Humanities*, vol. 6, no.
S1, 2018, pp. 167–174.

DOI:
[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.1404507](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1404507)

K. ShobithaKumari, M.Com

Assistant Professor, Jain College- CGS, V V Puram, Bangalore

Dr.M.P.Saravanan, MBA, NET, Ph.D

Assistant Professor, Jain College-CGS, VV Puram, Bangalore

Shawar Saleem, M.Com, NET,

Assistant Professor, Jain College-CGS, V V Puram, Bangalore

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) like mobile sensors, robots, driverless cars are here to continuously evolve and transform human life.AI is intelligence exhibited by machines or software by continuous learning.AI is transforming nature of almost everything which is connected to human life like employment, communication, health care etc.For example jobs like accountant, tele callers or desk officer will be mentioned in past tense in some decades.In this context we explore how AI or automation is likely to affect employment opportunities. Some people fear that automation is big threat to employment. But on the other hand there are people who feel it as a part of overall societal development and also create more job opportunities. So we undertook a survey on perceptual study on impact of automation among information technology employees.All the respondents who took part in survey were screened to make sure that they have basic knowledge on automation.The findings of the study indicate that even though they accept that automation will change their job profile, they also perceive that there will be no threat by automation in their jobs. The study was carried out in Bangalore city with special reference to Information Technology(IT) field.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Automation in employment, Artificial intelligence and IT industry, Automation

Introduction

“Artificial Intelligence - here I come, upgrade yourself or I will make u abscond”.

It sounds so dramatic, but in future this is what going to happen unless each and every employee is aware of what is happening in present world and what is that extra thing he should have to compete with technology. Artificial intelligencesometimes called machine intelligence is the intelligence demonstrated by machines, in contrast to natural intelligence displayed by humans and other animals.C. Frey and M. Osborne (2013), argue that there are sectors

like telemarketers, programme writers where complete computerization might take place. However a dentist or a clergy cannot be replaced by automation.

Source: "The Future of Employment: How Susceptible are Jobs to Computerisation?", by C. Frey and M. Osborne (2013)

AI proves to be very effective in handling even more complex activities. They prove to be faster, more accurate reliable and cheaper than corresponding team of humans. It doesn't sleep, need breaks, get sick or take vacations, and it doesn't need health insurance or retirement benefits. It can work around the clock, is much faster than you are, can instantly scale to levels that human workers can't simply achieve, can quickly acquire and learn new skills, and it doesn't make mistakes. So, if you can't fight AI, then what can you do to safeguard your future employment? The first step is to get yourself educated about it. Artificial Intelligence rather than destroying jobs, it redefines them. While it's true that many low-skill jobs will fall by the wayside, replaced by the sophisticated automation, AI will create new careers and industries will emerge that haven't been invented yet.

Statement of problems

Even though it is said that there will be a stream of new business opportunities that will be created by use of Artificial Intelligence in automation, there is a great fear among people regarding what will happen to their job opportunities if machines start doing all the major work done by human beings till date. So we try to capture the perception of the IT employees on the future of their job scenario and impending automation.

Review of Literature

J Gregory(1982), member of National Association of office workers has done a research paper on “ "RACE AGAINST TIME: AUTOMATION OF THE OFFICE: AN ANALYSIS OF THE TRENDS IN OFFICE AUTOMATION AND THE IMPACT ON THE OFFICE WORKFORCE", where in a study was made on how new technology is being developed to computerize the very flow of work in the office, its potential impact is qualitatively different from previous office equipment which “mechanized” or “automated” routine tasks.

Margrethe h Olson(1982) , New York has done a research paper on “impact of office Automation on the Organization” .wherein study was made on potential impacts of office automation on the

organization and it stresses the need, when implementing automated office systems, to take a broad perspective of their potential positive and negative effects on the organization.

Ida RussakoffHoos(1960) has done a research paper on “Impact of Automation on workers” wherein the author makes an attempt to access long term results of office automation either for workers concerned or for the economy in general

Paul Osterman(1986), Associate professor of economics at Boston university, conducted a study on “Impact of computers on Employment of clerks and managers”, and found that that the net effect of computers in 1972–78 was to depress the employment of clerks and managers substantially, but that the pattern over time—a larger displacement effect in the first few years, followed by increased clerical and managerial employment—supports the bureaucratic reorganization hypothesis.

Alen L Porter(1987)Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, has done a research on “A TWO FACTOR MODEL OF THE EFFECTS OF OFFICE AUTOMATION ON EMPLOYMENT” wherein he found out thatoffice automation will enhance productivity,office workload is apt to increase in response to enhanced information handling capabilities, implying demand for additional workers

LeneKromann, Jan Rose Skaksen, Anders Sørensen(2011), Copenhagen Business School has done a study on” Automation, labor productivity and employment – a cross country comparison”, they found out that that First, automation increases labor productivity; second, that automation decreases employment in the short run; third, that automation increases employment in the long run.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To understand the impact of Artificial Intelligence on IT industry
- 2) To find out the perception of IT employees on automation
- 3) To find out impact of Automation on IT employees

Based on the above mentioned objectives the following hypotheses were developed.

H1:There is significant difference between employee’s gender and their perception on automation.

H2:There is significant difference between employee’s age and their perception on automation.

H3:There is significant difference between employee’s educational qualification and their perception on automation.

H4:There is significant difference between employee’s job experience and their perception on automation.

H5:There is significant difference between employee’s designation and their perception on automation.

Scope of the study

This study helps in understanding the perception of the IT employees on automation and its impact on their jobs in the future in Bangalore. The same study may be applicable to other industries as well.

Limitations of the study

- 1) Research is confined only to a limited sample size of 100
- 2) Research is confined only to impact on employment opportunities
- 3) Research is confined to only IT employees

Research Methodology

The authors would like to specifically focus on perception about automation and how does it will have an impact on their jobs in the future.

Descriptive research design

Descriptive research is a type of research design is description of current state of affairs as it is at present. A close ended online questionnaire was administered to the respondents.

Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling technique was employed in selection of sample.

Sample Size

The sample size of this study constitutes the IT employees with the total sample size of 100.

Data Collection methods

A questionnaire was used to collect primary data, since primary data is one original in nature.

Statistical tools

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 24 and AMOS.

Data analysis and interpretation

Table No.1 Demographic Details of the respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents	%
Male	68	68
Female	42	42
Total	100	100
Age		
20 to 30 years	52	52
31 to 40 years	32	32
41 to 50 years	12	12
> 50 years	4	4
Total	100	100
Educational Qualification		
Diploma	16	16
Degree	32	32
Post Graduate	52	52
Total	100	100
Experience		
< 1 year	20	20
1-5 years	44	44
> 5 Years	36	36
Total	100	100

From the above table it is inferred that out of the total respondents total 68% were male and 42% were female. 52 % of the respondents belongs to age group of 20 to 30 years of age and 32 % belong to age group of 31 to 40. out of the total respondents 12 % belong to the age group of 41 to 50 years. 32 % of respondents have post graduate qualification , 52% are undergraduates and 16% are diploma holders. 44% have 1 to 5 years work experience and 36% respondents have more than 5 years work experience.

Table 3 Scope for Automation in different Departments

Departments	No.
Production	81
Accounting and Finance	7
HR Department	7
Research and Development	13
Marketing Department	10

It is inferred from the above table that most influenced department on implementing of automation is production department.

Table 4 Perception on Implementation of Automation in their Jobs

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
Increased Productivity	2.92	.394
Helps in better Decision Making	2.80	.492
More Accuracy	2.64	.560
Time Saving	2.40	.492
Reduced Workload	2.32	.737

It is inferred from the above table that most of them believe implementing automation will increase their productivity (mean=2.92) followed by helps in decision making (mean=2.80)

Table 5 Perception on Automation's Impact on Business Organization

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
Automation will allow us to New Business	2.88	.327
Will gain Competitive Advantage	2.88	.433
To have better Control on workforce	2.84	.368
I feel it will lead to a tremendous Job Fall	1.96	.875

It is inferred from the above table that most of the employees feel that automation will allow a business organization to move into new business and it will help in gaining competitive advantage as well (mean=2.88). and few (mean=1.96) feel that it will lead to job fall in future.

Table 6 Perception about the Impact of Automation on Job of Individual

Items	Frequency	%
I don't think any threat to my job	48	48.0
No Idea	32	32.0
I might lose my job	20	20.0
Total	100	100.0

It is inferred from the above table that 48% of respondents feels that automation is not a threat to their job. Whereas 32% of respondents have no idea on what will be impact of automation on their job.

Diagram 1: Path Analysis on the Employee’s Perception Towards Impact of Automation

Chi-square:76.191, RMR: .039, GFI :.956, AGFI:.914, RMSEA:.073

Table 7 Regression Weights

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Gender	→ Impact of Automation	-.390	.133	-2.935	.003
Age	→ Impact of Automation	-.005	.095	-.056	.956
Educational Qualification	→ Impact of Automation	.090	.084	1.078	.281
Experience	→ Impact of Automation	-.698	.085	-8.228	***
Designation	→ Impact of Automation	.125	.098	1.272	.203

From the path analysis we can conclude that the gender and experience have a significant effect on the perception on automation where the p value is less than 05.

Table 8 Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Result
H1: There is significant difference between employee’s gender and their perception on automation.	Accepted
H2: There is significant difference between employee’s age and their perception on automation.	Rejected
H3: There is significant difference between employee’s educational qualification and their perception on automation.	Rejected
H4: There is significant difference between employee’s job experience and their perception on automation.	Accepted
H5: There is significant difference between employee’s designation and their perception on automation.	Rejected

Out of the five hypotheses formulated only two were found to be significant. Only age and job experience have a significant difference in the perception of automation and all other variables (age, educational qualification and designation) did not affect the perception on automation.

Findings

The researchers found out that out of the total respondents majority were male respondents and majority of the respondents belongs to the age group of 20-30. Most of the respondents have post graduation qualification. And most of them have more than 1 years work experience. The respondents feel that production department is the one where there will be highest possibility of implementation of artificial intelligence. And most of them feel that it will help in increase productivity as well as great support in decision making. Respondents are also of opinion that from the point of view of business organization it will help in gaining competitive advantage and will help in expanding business. Most of them those who have more than a year experience are in favor of implementation of Artificial intelligence and feels no threat to their job in future. Most of the respondents think they will not lose their jobs because of automation. The above results provide a picture on what are the major elements that influence the implementation of automation. It is evident from hypothesis analysis that gender and work experience have great impact on perception on implementation of automation and all other variables (age, educational qualification and designation) did not affect the perception on automation. According to the results it is very clear that employees are ready to welcome the developments in technology

Suggestions

It is evident from the study that few low level employers have a fear that they will be replaced by artificial intelligence or automation. Society needs to provide education and job placement opportunities for those who will be most affected by automation. By providing proper training on upgraded technology company can prepare its employees to withstand the implementation of artificial intelligence. Updated knowledge imparting is the best solution to those who fear that their jobs on fire. Governmental have to implement policy to encourage technology education to all graduates irrespective of the course. Acquiring of better computer skills will be a blessing for employees in any field. To remain relevant in the Age of Automation, IT pros must be fluent in so-called “soft” skills like strategic and critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and anticipation. Most important, our future relevancy depends on our ability to learn new skills on the fly — to adapt quickly to new and emerging technologies and position ourselves to do the things for our clients that those new technologies can’t do. Not long ago, we could count on our degrees and on-the-job experience to carry us for decades and build our careers.

Conclusion

The main objective of the study is to find out impact of implementation of artificial intelligence on employment opportunities. Study revealed that there are major portion of employees who wants artificial intelligence to be implemented in their business. Organizations are looking for faster outputs, improved quality, and higher profits. Consumers want excellent products at a lower price. The demand to do more with less has been driving innovators, engineers and technology gurus to develop robotic replacements much like the machine replacements from the industrial revolution. Though many jobs are in danger of disappearing, a change in skills may still keep them alive. Success of any business organization depends on how well a company can blend its human resources with technology without eliminating any employees. Employees are ready to welcome development in technology.

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